

Utilization of Organic Waste as Sustainable Electrical Bioenergy with Microbial Fuel Cell Method

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Abstract

The problem of organic waste is not new in the world, but so far organic waste management has only become fertilizer. Organic waste is solid waste that is easy to rot and causes a very strong odor, so it requires new management innovations. The use of electrical energy sourced from non-renewable and unsustainable materials can cause environmental problems such as air pollution, noise pollution, and waste pollution. The two problems that occur in Indonesia that both cause a lot of disadvantages, especially in the environment, can be turned into a benefit that will help overcome the problem, namely by utilizing microbial fuel cell technology. The manufacture of Microbial fuel cells with the main substrate in the form of organic waste has the aim of solving environmental problems due to organic waste and non-renewable and unsustainable sources of electrical energy. Microbial fuel cells have four main components, namely substrate, anode, proton exchange membrane, and cathode. The working principle of the microbial fuel cell is to take advantage of bacterial interactions that occur in organic waste and the results of interactions in the form of chemical energy are converted into electrical energy. The electrical energy generated by microbial fuel cells can solve the problem of electrical energy sources and organic waste. Microbial fuel cells in the future are expected to be able to become an alternative energy source that is environmentally friendly and sustainable. Low electrical power as well as the selection of the right organic waste substrate are challenges in development.

Keywords: *Organic Waste, Bioenergy, MFC*

1. Introduction

Waste falsification in Indonesia is a problem that does not need to be a surprise anymore because it has become a public secret. Organic waste is a complex problem that must be addressed by developing countries including Indonesia, which every year the waste management data is still fluctuating. Based on data obtained from the Directorate General of Waste, Waste and B3 Management (Ditjen PSLB3) of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) in 2021, which states that the volume of waste in Indonesia is recorded at 68.5 million tons, and in 2022 it will increase to 70 million tons. From this figure, a little waste is absorbed to be recycled again. Meanwhile, everyday waste continues to be produced by each individual. Most of the waste generation is classified as organic waste derived from household waste, business centers, and traditional markets. Organic waste is solid waste that is easy to rot and causes a very pungent

odor, so it causes a lot of harm to humans. Based on data from the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) in 2021, the most type of organic waste are food waste, which is 40%. However, the organic waste only ends up in a landfill (TPA) and then the waste will become a mountain that is ready to erupt and harm the environment and the surrounding community because there is still a lack of proper management.

Over time, the country will always grow with an increase in population and an increase in its activities. This of course will also cause an increase in the volume of waste, so proper management is needed on each type of waste pile they produce. Good waste management is one of the factors that influence the creation of a clean and healthy environment. Waste management in Indonesia is still not optimally carried out. Most of the waste ends up in the landfill, then over time the landfill is no longer able to accommodate the waste produced, so the waste is thrown into an open area that will cause soil pollution, a nest of germs that can cause disease in humans or also be disposed of in waterways which also causes water pollution and blockage of water flow.

In addition to the problem of garbage piles, one of the problems that are no less big is that Indonesia still has a high dependence on electricity production from non-renewable and environmentally unfriendly power plants. Indonesia has power sources such as Pembangkit Listrik Tenaga Diesel (PLTD), Pembangkit Listrik Tenaga Bayu (PLTB), Pembangkit Listrik Tenaga Mesin Gas (PLTMG), Pembangkit Listrik Tenaga Uap (PLTU). Based on data from PT Perusahaan Listrik Negara (Persero) or PLN, it is reported that the number of power generation units amounted to 6,143 units at the end of 2021. Of these, as many as 5,258 units are types of Pembangkit Listrik Tenaga Diesel (PLTD). The portion reaches 85.59% of the total power generation units used. Meanwhile, the sustainable use of this PLTD will cause environmental problems such as air pollution, noise pollution, and B3 waste pollution. The two problems that occur in Indonesia that both cause a lot of excitement, especially in the environment, can be turned into a benefit that will help overcome the problem, namely by applying microbial fuel cell technology. A microbial fuel cell or known as MFC is an electrical energy generation system by utilizing bacterial interactions found in nature. Bacteria contained in the organic medium convert organic matter into electrical energy. This innovation will turn waste into an energy source that will help meet the needs of the Indonesian people.

2. Body Paragraph

Microbial fuel cell (MFC) is a bioelectrochemical-based power generation system that utilizes microorganisms available in nature (Zulfikar *et al*, 2021). According to (Chaturvedi & Verma, 2016) MFC is a method of utilizing the ability of bacteria to convert metabolic reactions which are chemical energy from organic matter into electrical energy. Another opinion states that MFC is a device that uses the main active ingredient in the form of bacteria as a catalyst to oxidize organic and inorganic materials and produce a current (Logan *et al*, 2006). These definitions clearly explain that MFC is a device capable of being a power generation system by utilizing the ability of bacteria to convert chemical energy from metabolic

reactions to oxidize organic and inorganic materials into electrical energy and generate current.

Quite some bacteria can be used as active ingredients of MFC, such as *Shewanella oneidensis* strain 14063 (Fernando *et al*, 2012), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strain L17 (Liu *et al*, 2009), and others. All of the examples mentioned have one thing in common, namely these bacteria can transmit electrons through a biological membrane to or from the extracellular environment, so these bacteria are called electroactive bacteria (EB) (Rabaey *et al*, 2010). Due to the ability of bacteria to transport the generated electrons to the external environment, these bacteria can be used as MFC agents.

The main component of the MFC consists of 4 parts (Fig 1.), namely the substrate, anode, proton exchange membrane (PEM), and cathode. The substrate is the material that becomes the source or will be modified by bacteria, the anode is the place where oxidation reactions occur (positive pole), and the PEM is an electrochemical device that can convert chemical energy directly into electrical energy (Kong & Cheng, 2017), the cathode is the place where reduction reaction (negative pole). The bacteria that play a role in this MFC are at the anode, and convert the substrate into carbon dioxide (CO₂), protons, and electrons. Systematically, the working concept of MFC (Chaturvedi & Verma, 2016) is that the electrons produced are then transferred to the cathode space while the protons pass through the membrane. The reaction between protons and electrons in the cathode space using the oxygen will form water and as long as there is a substrate, the substrate will continue to undergo modifications and changes, so the electrons will continue to flow and generate electricity.

Fig 1. Illustration of MFC

Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) are bio-electrochemical gadgets that could at once convert chemical energy in biodegradable organic matter to electrical energy by way of exoelectrogenic bacteria as catalysts. Mukhaifi & Salwa (2019) stated that to use MFCs in electricity generation, the produced electrons ought to be moved out of the cell's electron transport chain and deposited on an electrode. In MFC method, the anode is the bacteria-identified terminal electron acceptor within the anodic chamber. Therefore the microbial interest depends strongly on the

redox capacity of the anode. To transform this electric contemporary into usable power, exoelectrogen must be positioned in a fuel cell.

MFC can solve the electrical problem by using exoelectrogenic bacteria. Bacteria in MFC can oxidize complex organic matter in waste and produce electrons that can be used as a supply of electrical energy because of the potential difference that takes place. These bacteria can extract electrons from the energy supply (oxidation) and transfer them to the anode via diverse extracellular electron transfer (EET) mechanisms (anodic respiration). The ensuing electrons are then transported to the cathode and used for the reduction reaction of oxidized compounds which generates electric energy. Through MFC technology, part of the energy produced can be taken within the form of electricity. Ali *et al.*, (2019) stated that MFC technology produces an equal quantity of voltage of 998 mV. It is also stated that the bacteria growth rate in MFC has the fundamental function on the increased voltage production, overall count of bacteria was measured in MFC, and it was discovered that voltage increases within the growth rate of bacteria and started to drops when bacteria activities decrease. So that's why MFC can solve an electrical problem.

MFC can be a part of sustainable bioenergy because Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) is a renewable source of energy that produces electricity without causing any pollution that harms the environment. Basically, bacteria can digest pretty much anything. By using specific bacteria through MFC technology, it could be used to generate power with biodegradable waste and sewage, which is very widely available. At the same time, it could also get rid of waste and provide help with wastewater treatment and bioremediation. That's why it can be considered part of sustainable bioenergy.

MFC has many advantages, such as assisting lessen environmental contaminants which include wastewater, reducing atmospheric carbon dioxide by using it to rebuild fuels and might doubtlessly provide a renewable power supply. This technology can generate electricity from biowastes and organic matter. MFC could convert the energy of the substrate into electricity. MFC can also be bioremediation of toxic compounds.

3. Conclusion

MFC has bright prospects in the future as an alternative source of electrical energy. MFC shows its potential as an integrated system for sustainable bioenergy as well as sewage treatment. MFC technology on a lab scale has met the essential requirements of a power plant. However, although it has been said to have a potential power plant, the output power of MFC is classified as low which is a major problem in this field. Another challenge to note is the selection of the right organic waste substrate because the work of MFC depends on the utilization of the substrate by microbes so the selection of the substrate greatly affects the efficiency of the MFC. Although MFC has various challenges that will be faced in the future as sustainable bioenergy, it is undeniable that this MFC is a solution to two problems that occur in Indonesia, namely organic waste and non-renewable and unsustainable sources of electrical energy.

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